

Direct spectrophotometric determination of metronidazole and ornidazole

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Manuscript received 10 May 2011, revised 02 November 2011, accepted 21 November 2011

Abstract : A direct spectrophotometric method was developed by the authors, for the detection and determination of metronidazole and ornidazole in pure form, as well in pharmaceutical formulations in the form of tablets and capsules. The method was based on the formation of an instantaneous, clear, stable, reddish-purple colour, due to the diazotization reaction between the nitro group of the drug sample, sulphanilamide and NEDA. The drug sample, dissolved in hot water, followed by the addition of 2 ml of each 0.5% sulphanilamide and 0.3% NEDA, exhibited a stable reddish purple colour, which showed a maximum absorbance at 540 nm. Beer's law was found to be obeyed in the range of 200–600 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for metronidazole and 100–360 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for ornidazole with a limit of detection of 0.01 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and 0.02 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ respectively. The method was found to be simple, accurate and recommended for rapid analysis.

Keywords : Metronidazole, ornidazole, NEDA, sulphanilamide, spectrophotometry.

Introduction

5-Nitroimidazoles, such as metronidazole and ornidazole, are extensively used as anti-amoebic, anti-protozoal and specific anti-bacterial drugs. The discovery of the anti-bacterial and anti-trichomonal properties of the antibiotic azomycin led to the investigation of nitroimidazoles as anti-parasitic agents. Although the amoebicidal properties of metronidazole were studied, it was not clinically tested until some years later. In clinical tests, metronidazole is effective against intestinal amoebiasis in rats and hepatic amoebiasis in hamsters and is also active *in vitro* against *E. histolytica*. The initial clinical tests of metronidazole indicated that it was capable of curing amoebic dysentery and amoebic liver abscess. Subsequent clinical tests have established metronidazole as the effective drug of choice, in the treatment of all forms of amoebiasis, in humans.

Variation of the structure of metronidazole, principally to improve trichomonocidal activity and metabolic stability, led to the discovery of other anti-amoebic agents. Ornidazole falls into the same category of drugs. Ornidazole [1-chloro-3-(2-methyl-5-nitro-1*H*-imidazol-1-yl)propane-2-ol] with chemical formula $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{10}\text{ClN}_3\text{O}_3$ is a drug, that cures some protozoan infections. It is also used in the poultry industry. It has been investigated for use in Crohn's disease, also known as regional enteritis, which is an inflammation of the intestines, that may affect any part of the gastrointestinal tract. It primarily causes ab-

dominal pain, dysentery, vomiting, or weight loss, but may also cause complications outside the gastrointestinal tract, such as skin allergy, arthritis, inflammation of the eye, tiredness etc.

In literature³⁻¹⁵, it was found that various reagents such as *p*-dimethylcinnamaldehyde, 4-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, β -naphthol, metol-potassium dichromate, *N,N*-dimethylphenylenediamine and chloramine-T, vanillin, salicylaldehyde, bromocresol purple, bromocresol green, NaOH-KCl, bromothymol blue, methylbenzothiazolin-2-onehydrazine (MTBH), and NEDA were used as chromogens for the spectrophotometric determination of the drug samples after the reduction of the nitro group in them. The reduced amino compound is then diazotized. The procedures proposed in literature³⁻¹⁵ involve tedious and time consuming reduction processes. The method developed by the authors was found to be less time consuming, accurate and precise.

Most of the above spectrophotometric methods, found by the authors in the literature³⁻¹⁵ for the determination of metronidazole and ornidazole in the visible region involve, initial reduction by treatment with Zn and HCl followed by the diazotization and coupling of the resulting amine. All these methods involve tedious time consuming procedures, such as heating and extraction, costly reagents and an additional diazotization step, limiting the accuracy. The present one developed by the authors was a direct, accurate, precise and reproducible spectropho-

tometric method, for the detection and determination of metronidazole and ornidazole, in pure form and in pharmaceutical formulations. The authors method was devoid of reduction procedures and as such was found to increase the accuracy.

Experimental

Reagents :

The pure form of sample of metronidazole¹ was prepared in our laboratory and ornidazole was obtained commercially. These pure crystalline products were standardized by the standard method^{1,2}.

Metronidazole and ornidazole tablets :

Ten tablets each of metronidazole and ornidazole of different pharmaceutical firms under study, were weighed and ground into a fine powder. From this, a sample of 500 mg was weighed and dissolved in 150 ml of double distilled water. This solution is heated to a temperature of 90 °C for 90 min. After complete dissolution, the cool solution was filtered through a Whatmann No. 40 filter paper. The clear solution was made upto the mark into a 100 volumetric flask and standardized^{1,2}.

0.5% Sulphanilamide in 20% (v/v) hydrochloric acid :

A stock solution of 0.5% sulphanilamide was prepared by dissolving an accurate amount of 0.5 g of sulphanilamide in 20% hydrochloric acid and the solution was made up to the mark, in a 100 ml volumetric flask using 20% hydrochloric acid.

0.3% NEDA solution in 1% (v/v) hydrochloric acid :

A stock solution of 0.3% NEDA was prepared by dissolving an accurate amount of 0.3 g of NEDA in 1% hydrochloric acid. The solution was made up to the mark in a 100 ml volumetric flask, using 1% hydrochloric acid.

All the reagents used were of AnalaR grade only.

Apparatus :

An ELICO SL-177 scanning visible spectrophotometer was used for all absorbance measurements. Matched set of 1 cm glass/quartz cuvettes were used. Shimadzu-AUX 220 digital electronic balance was used for all weighing measurements. An ELICO LI-127 pH-meter was used for all pH measurements.

Recommended procedure for the determination of metronidazole and ornidazole :

An aliquot (2.0 ml) of drug sample of both metronidazole and ornidazole was mixed with 2 ml each of 0.5%

sulphanilamide and 0.3% NEDA solution, to give an instantaneous, clear, stable, reddish-purple coloured product. Each of the mixture was made upto 50 ml in a volumetric flask and the spectra were taken for each of an aliquot of the solutions, which showed a λ_{\max} at 540 nm (Figs. 1 and 2).

Fig. 1. Absorption spectrum of the reddish-purple coloured product obtained by the reaction between metronidazole, sulphanilamide and NEDA. The λ_{\max} is 540 nm.

Fig. 2. Absorption spectrum of the reddish-purple coloured product obtained by the reaction between ornidazole, sulphanilamide and NEDA. The λ_{\max} is 540 nm.

Table 1. Optical characteristics and validation data

Parameters	Metronidazole	Ornidazole
λ_{\max} (nm)	540	540
Beer's law limit ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	200–600	100–300
Molar absorptivity ($\text{cm}^{-1} \text{L mol}^{-1}$)	72.68	91.14
Stability (<i>h</i>)	> 24	>24
Correlation coefficient (<i>r</i>)	0.9979	0.9985
Relative standard deviation (RSD ^{a*}) (%)	1.4	1.8
Limit of detection ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	0.01	0.005
Limit of quantification ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	0.04	0.015

^a10 replicate analysis of 200 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$.

Table 2. Analysis for metronidazole and ornidazole formulations

Commercial formulations analyzed	PM ^a	SM ^b	RSD ^c
Metrogyl (500 mg)	100.2	100.0	1.5
Flagyl (500 mg)	99.8	99.9	1.8
Ornidazole (300 mg)	98.7	99.8	1.9
Ornidazole (500 mg)	99.5	99.9	1.4

^aProposed method. ^bStandard method. ^c10 replicate analysis.

For the determination of metronidazole and ornidazole, an aliquot volume (2.0 ml) of the sample solution was mixed with 2 ml each of 0.5% sulphanilamide and 0.3% NEDA solutions, to give a stable, clear, reddish-purple coloured product. The mixture was made upto 50 ml in a volumetric flask. The solution was taken in an optically matched cuvette of ELICO SL-177 spectrophotometer and the absorbances were measured at 540 nm. The absorbances were compared with the standard curve (Figs. 3 and 4). Beer's law was found to be valid over the range 200–600 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for metronidazole (Fig. 3) and 100–300 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for ornidazole (Fig. 4).

Results and discussion

The instantaneous, clear, reddish-purple colour obtained for metronidazole and ornidazole, with sulphanilamide and NEDA was determined at a λ_{\max} of 540 nm. There was no overlap of spectra of other components used. It was observed that the reaction was dependent on the pH as well as on the concentration of the reagents. Below and above the pH values of 3.5, the colour produced was found to be unstable. The reddish-purple colour of the product was obtained and stable with 0.5% sulphanilamide and 0.3% NEDA solutions. Below the concentration level, the colour developed was found to be unstable and higher concentrations was found to have

Fig. 3. Calibration plot for estimation of metronidazole. Beer's law obtained was 200–600 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ at λ_{\max} is 540.

Fig. 4. Calibration plot for estimation of ornidazole. Beer's law obtained was 100–600 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ at λ_{\max} 540 nm.

no effect on the colour. Hence the concentrations of the reagents were fixed by the authors as 0.5% and 0.3% for sulphanilamide and NEDA respectively. All the observations were made after attaining stable absorbance in 30 min.

Beer's law was found to be valid over the range 200–600 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for metronidazole and 100–300 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for ornidazole. The calculated molar absorptivity (ϵ) of metronidazole was $72.68 \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ L mol}^{-1}$ and that of ornidazole was $91.14 \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ L mol}^{-1}$. Detection limits (LOD) of metronidazole were $0.01 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and that of ornidazole was $0.005 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. The limit of quantitation (LOQ) for metronidazole was $0.04 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and that of ornidazole was $0.015 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. The correlation factor for metronidazole was 0.9979 and 0.9985 for ornidazole. Relative standard deviation calculated for 10 measurements for each of the sample of drug was found to be in the limit prescribed, such as 1.4% for metronidazole and 1.8% for ornidazole. The lower values of RSD indicate the good precision and reproducibility of the method, developed by the authors. From the data, it was found that the LOQ values were 3.3 times greater than the LOD values. LOD was well below the lower limit of the Beer's law range. Commonly used excipients and other additives such as glucose, dextrose, lactose, starch, sodium alginate, talc, magnesium alginate and magnesium stearate and ascorbic acid, had no interferences. These results were found to be accurate, precise and reproducible.

Conclusions :

The solutions of metronidazole and ornidazole gave an instantaneous, clear, stable reddish-purple coloured product, with 0.5% sulphanilamide and 0.3% NEDA solutions, at a pH of 3.5. The λ_{max} for the reddish-purple colour product was 540 nm, with molar absorptivities of $72.68 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $91.14 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 540 nm. Beer's law was valid over the range 200–600 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for metronidazole and 100–300 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for ornidazole. The determination of the drug samples by author's method was rapid, accurate and hence recommended.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the management of Maharajah's Post Graduate College, Vizianagaram, Andhra Pradesh for the facilities provided, consistent support and encouragement.

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